

Harmonic dualism: inventories

The inventories below serve as ways to categorize the sources on harmonic dualism presented in the annotated bibliography. They show overlapping themes, such as the theorists that put forth theories on harmonic dualism and authors that discuss these theorists or the relation between theories and scientific branches. The resting inventories create links between the sources that help relate them in other ways, such as a chronological order or the way in which the sources can be applied. The 91 sources, including translations, gathered in the annotated bibliography are placed within each inventory and sub-division that they relate to, and thus recur multiple times. Translations are, again, indicated with the initials "TR" (translation). Each inventory is provided with a short introduction to provide some more information on their specific division.

Theorists

Many theorists have come up with theories on harmonic dualism, and many more have written about their theories. The most important figure in the development of these theories is Hugo Riemann. This first inventory provides an overview of the theorists that have come up with or at least in some way altered existing theories on harmonic dualism. On a bigger level the theorists are organised in a timely relation to Riemann: those that go before him, Riemann himself, and then theorists that came after him. A further division is made based on the theorists' nationalities, to show to what extent these theories were alive in different countries.

Pre-Riemann

Germany

Hauptmann

Bernstein, D. W. (1993). Symmetry and Symmetrical Inversion in Turn-of-the-Century Theory and Practice. In *Music Theory and the Exploration of the Past*, ed. Christopher Hatch and David W. Bernstein, pp. 377-407. University of Chicago Press.

Bernstein, D. W. (2002). Nineteenth-century harmonic theory: the Astro-German legacy. In *The Cambridge History of Western Music Theory*. Cambridge University Press.

Burnham, S. (1992). Method and Motivation in Hugo Riemann's History of Harmonic Theory. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 14(1), 1-14.

Dahlhaus, C. (1989). *Die Geschichte der Musiktheorie im 18. und 19. Jahrhundert, Zweiter Teil*. Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft.

(TR) Dahlhaus, C. (1990). *Studies on the Origins of Harmonic Tonality*. Translated by Robert Gjerdingen. Princeton University Press.

Ehrhardt, D. (2010). "Théories riemannienne, néo-riemannienne et post-riemannienne: Perspectives pour l'harmonie et l'interprétation musicales." In *Vers une musicologie de l'interprétation*, edited by Jean-Pierre Armengaud and Damien Ehrhardt, 133-79. L'Harmattan.

- Harrison, D. (1994). *Harmonic Function in Chromatic Music: A Renewed Dualist Theory and an Account of Its Precedents*. University of Chicago Press.
- Hauptmann, M. (1853). *Die Natur der Harmonik und der Metrik*. Breitkopf und Härtel.
 (TR) Hauptmann, M. (1888). *The Nature of Harmony and Metre*. Translated and edited by W.E. Heathcote. Swan Sonnenschein & Co.
- Jorgenson, D. (1963). A Résumé of Harmonic Dualism. *Music & Letters*, 44(1), 31–42.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/733108>
- Klumpenhouwer, H. (2002). Dualist tonal space and transformation in nineteenth-century musical thought. In *The Cambridge History of Western Music Theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- Kopp, D. (2002). *Chromatic Transformations in Nineteenth-Century Music*. Cambridge University Press.
- Levarie, S. (1992). Musical polarity: major and minor. *International Journal of Musicology*, 1, 29-45.
- Mickelsen, W. C. (1977). *Hugo Riemann's Theory of Harmony and History of Music Theory, Book III*. University of Nebraska Press.
- Notley, M. (2005). Plagal Harmony as Other: Asymmetrical Dualism and Instrumental Music by Brahms. *The Journal of Musicology*, 22(1), 90–130. <https://doi.org/10.1525/jm.2005.22.1.90>.
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- Riemann, H. (1882). Die Natur der Harmonik. *Sammlung Musikalische Vorträge 4.40*. Breitkopf und Härtel.
 (TR) Steege, B. (2011). "The Nature of Harmony": A Translation and Commentary. In *The Oxford Handbook of Neo-Riemannian Music Theories*, 55-91. Oxford University Press.
- Riemann, H. (1914-1915). Ideen zu einer 'Lehre von den Tonvorstellungen'. *Jahrbuch der Musikbibliothek Peters*, 21-22, 1-26.
 (TR) Wason, R. & Marvin, E. W. (1992). Riemann's 'Ideen zu einer Lehre von den Tonvorstellungen': An annotated Translation. *Journal of Music Theory*, 36(1), 69-117.
- Riley, M. (2004). The "Harmonic Major" Mode in Nineteenth-Century Theory and Practice. *Music Analysis*, 23(1), 1–26. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3700427>.
- Rummenheller, P. (1966). Moritz Hauptmann, der Begründer einer transzendental-dialektischen Musiktheorie. In *Beiträge zur Musiktheorie des 19. Jahrhunderts*, 11-38. Gustav Bosse.
- Sekimoto, N. (2007). Jean-Adam Serre (1704-1788) était-il dualiste? La justification de l'origine du mode mineur dans ses "Essais sur les principes de l'harmonie (1753)". *Musurgia*, 14(2), 7-34.
- Shirlaw, M. (1969). *The theory of harmony: An inquiry into the Natural Principles of Harmony, with an Explanation of the Chief Systems of Harmony from Rameau to the Present Day*. Reprint, Da Capo Press.
- Vogel, M. (1966). Arthur von Oettingen und der Harmonische Dualismus. In *Beiträge zur Musiktheorie im 19. Jahrhundert*, 4, 103-132. Gustav Bosse.

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<http://www.jstor.org/stable/765324>.

Oettingen

Bernstein, D. W. (1993). Symmetry and Symmetrical Inversion in Turn-of-the-Century Theory and Practice. In *Music Theory and the Exploration of the Past*, ed. Christopher Hatch and David W. Bernstein, pp. 377-407. University of Chicago Press.

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Burnham, S. (1992). Method and Motivation in Hugo Riemann's History of Harmonic Theory. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 14(1), 1-14.

Clark, Suzannah. 2001. "Seduced by Notation: Oettingen's Topography of the Major-Minor System." In *Music Theory and Natural Order from the Renaissance to the Early Twentieth Century*, edited by Suzannah Clark and Alexander Rehding, 161–180. Cambridge University Press.

Dahlhaus, C. (1989). *Die Geschichte der Musiktheorie im 18. und 19. Jahrhundert, Zweiter Teil*. Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft.

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Mickelsen, W. C. (1977). *Hugo Riemann's Theory of Harmony and History of Music Theory, Book III*. University of Nebraska Press.

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Riemann

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Byrne, D. A. (2018). *The Harmonic Theories of Sigfrid Karg-Elert: Acoustics, Function, Transformation, Perception* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Cincinnati]. OhioLINK Electronic Theses and Dissertations Center. http://rave.ohiolink.edu/etdc/view?acc_num=ucin1522417315389199.

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Ehrhardt, D. (2010). "Théories riemannienne, néo-riemannienne et post-riemannienne: Perspectives pour l'harmonie et l'interprétation musicales." In *Vers une musicologie de l'interprétation*, edited by Jean-Pierre Armengaud and Damien Ehrhardt, 133-79. L'Harmattan.

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Ergo, M. (1914). *Ueber Richard Wagner's Harmonik und Melodik. Ein Beitrag zur Wagnerschen Harmonik*. Breitkopf & Härtel.

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Pearce, T. (2008). Tonal Functions and Active Synthesis: Hugo Riemann, German Psychology, and Kantian Epistemology. *Intégral*, 22, 81–116. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/20696499>.

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- Riemann, H. (1874). *Ueber das Musikalische Hören*. Dr. Phil. Diss., Göttingen University. Andrä.
- Riemann, H. (1877). *Musikalische Syntaxis: Grundriß einer harmonischen Satzbildungslehre*. Breitkopf und Härtel.
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- Riemann, H. (1887). *Handbuch der Harmonielehre*. Breitkopf und Härtel.
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- Riemann, H. (1893). *Vereinfachte Harmonielehre; oder, Die Lehre von den tonalen Funktionen der Akkorde*. Augener.
 (TR) Riemann, H. (1895). *Harmony Simplified: or, The theory of the tonal unctions of chords*. Translated by Henry Bewerunge. Augener and Company.
- Riemann, H. (1905). *Das problem des Harmonischen Dualismus: Ein Beitrag zur Ästhetik der Musik*. Verlag von C. F. Kahnt Nachfolger.
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 (TR) Riemann, H. (1930). *Armonía y modulación*. Translation by Antonio Ribera y Maneja. Editorial Labor.
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- Seidel, E. (1966). Die Harmonielehre Hugo Riemanns. In *Beiträge zur Musiktheorie im 19. Jahrhundert*, 39-92. Gustav Bosse.

Shirlaw, M. (1969). *The theory of harmony: An inquiry into the Natural Principles of Harmony, with an Explanation of the Chief Systems of Harmony from Rameau to the Present Day*. Reprint, Da Capo Press.

Tan, D. (2020). Dynamic dualism. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 42(1), 105-121.

Tymoczko, D. (2011). Dualism and the beholder's eye. In *The Oxford Handbook of Neo-Riemannian Music Theories*, 246-270. Oxford University Press.

Venturino, S. (2022). *Dualist Approaches to Resonance in French Music and Music Theory, 1900-1960*. Phd., University of Rochester.

Post-Riemann

Germany

Krehl

Harrison, D. (1994). *Harmonic Function in Chromatic Music: A Renewed Dualist Theory and an Account of Its Precedents*. University of Chicago Press.

Krehl, S. (1922). *Harmonielehre*. Vereinigung wissenschaftlicher Verleger.

Erpf

Erpf, H. (1927). *Studien zur Harmonie- und Klangtechnik der neueren Musik*. Breitkopf und Härtel

Erpf, H. (1930). *Harmonielehre in der Schule*. Quelle & Meyer

Harrison, D. (1994). *Harmonic Function in Chromatic Music: A Renewed Dualist Theory and an Account of Its Precedents*. University of Chicago Press.

Karg-Elert

Byrne, D. A. (2018). *The Harmonic Theories of Sigfrid Karg-Elert: Acoustics, Function, Transformation, Perception* [Doctoral dissertation, University of Cincinnati]. OhioLINK Electronic Theses and Dissertations Center. http://rave.ohiolink.edu/etdc/view?acc_num=ucin1522417315389199

Harrison, D. (1994). *Harmonic Function in Chromatic Music: A Renewed Dualist Theory and an Account of Its Precedents*. University of Chicago Press.

Jorgenson, D. (1963). A Résumé of Harmonic Dualism. *Music & Letters*, 44(1), 31–42.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/733108>.

Karg-Elert, S. (1921). *Die Grundlagen der Musiktheorie (Zweite Teil): Harmonielehre*. Speka-Musikalienverlag.

Karg-Elert, S. (1931). *Polaristische Klang- und Tonalitätslehre: (Harmonologik)*. Indiana University.
(TR) Karg-Elert, S. (2018). *Precepts on the Polarity of Sound and Tonality: (The Logic of Harmony)*. Translation by Harold Fabrikant and Staffan Thuringer. Publishing House of F. E. C. Leuckart.

Schenk, P. (1966). Karg-Elerts polarisierte Harmonielehre. In *Beiträge zur Musiktheorie des 19. Jahrhunderts*, 133-162. Gustav Bosse.

Austria

Mayrhofer

Thomson, P. (2010). *Robert Mayrhofer's Theory of Harmony* [Unpublished master's thesis]. University of Alberta.

Switzerland

Levy

Levy, E. (1985). *A Theory of Harmony*. SUNY Press.

Levarie, S. (1992). Musical polarity: major and minor. *International Journal of Musicology*, 1, 29-45.

France

d'Indy

d'Indy, V. (1912). *Cours de composition musicale, vol. 1 Third edition*. Compiled and edited by Auguste Sérieyx. Durand.

(TR) Montgomery, M. (1946). *A Comparative Analysis (and translation) of Vincent d'Indy's 'Cours de composition musicale'*. Dissertation.. Rochester University.

Godley, E. (1952). The minor triad. *Music & Letters*, 33(4), 285-295.

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Kieffer, A. (2016). Riemann in France: Jean Marnold and the “Modern” Music-Theoretical Ear. *Music Theory Spectrum*, 38(1), 1-15.

Venturino, S. (2022). *Dualist Approaches to Resonance in French Music and Music Theory, 1900-1960*. Phd., University of Rochester.

Bertelin

Bertelin, A. (1931). *Traité de composition musicale, volume 4*. Schola Cantorum.

Venturino, S. (2022). *Dualist Approaches to Resonance in French Music and Music Theory, 1900-1960*. Phd., University of Rochester.

Dommel-Diény

Dommel-Diény, A. (1958). *L'Harmonie vivante*. Delachaux et Niestl.

Venturino, S. (2022). *Dualist Approaches to Resonance in French Music and Music Theory, 1900-1960*. Phd., University of Rochester.

Perreau

Perreau, X. (1908). *La pluralité des modes et la théorie générale de la musique*. Fischbacher.

Venturino, S. (2022). *Dualist Approaches to Resonance in French Music and Music Theory, 1900-1960*. Phd., University of Rochester.

United States

Harrison

Harrison, D. (1994). *Harmonic Function in Chromatic Music: A Renewed Dualist Theory and an Account of Its Precedents*. University of Chicago Press.

Levarie (Austrian-born)

Klumpenhouwer, H. (2002). Dualist tonal space and transformation in nineteenth-century musical thought. In *The Cambridge History of Western Music Theory*. Cambridge University Press.

Levarie, S. (1992). Musical polarity: major and minor. *International Journal of Musicology*, 1, 29-45.

Link to science

Music theory has a long tradition of being part of or being linked to science. Theorists have examined harmonic dualism from different angles from acoustical sciences to metaphysical dialectics, physiology and psychology. This inventory shows to what scientific branch(es) harmonic dualism is linked to in the sources.

Acoustical sciences

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- Bernstein, D. W. (1993). Symmetry and Symmetrical Inversion in Turn-of-the-Century Theory and Practice. In *Music Theory and the Exploration of the Past*, ed. Christopher Hatch and David W. Bernstein, pp. 377-407. University of Chicago Press.
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Chronological order

This next inventory presents the sources in a chronological order, organised per decade. This shows when harmonic dualism was alive or when theories ebbed away and when they resurfaced. Translations are for this reason given separated from the original sources.

1850s

Hauptmann, M. (1853). *Die Natur der Harmonik und der Metrik*. Breitkopf und Härtel.

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Applicability

A last way to divide the sources is by their applicability. Many were intended as speculative studies on harmonic dualism, just for the sake of music theory or to give it a place among sciences. Other sources are meant to show the practical application of the theories, and some sources are even a combination of both. These sources meant as or containing information on the practical aspect can be further divided into two kinds: as compositional theory, and as an analytical tool.

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Practical application

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